

A Semi-empirical Model for Predicting Excess Enthalpies of Alkylbenzene Mixtures

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A semi-empirical model for predicting excess enthalpies of alkylbenzene mixtures is presented. The method treats alkylbenzene molecule as consisting of three types of surfaces, i.e. aromatic, C_6H_5 , and aliphatic, CH_3 and CH_2 , and considers three interaction parameters characterising interaction between aromatic-aliphatic, aromatic-aromatic and aliphatic-aliphatic surfaces. The model is also able to predict ΔH_v of alkylbenzenes.

The model assumes alkylbenzene molecule to be composed of three types of surfaces, i.e. aromatic, CH_3 and CH_2 . When two segments with different types of surfaces are in contact with each other, they have their own strength of interaction. However, it is assumed that CH_3 surface and CH_2 surface have similar interactions with aromatic surface and between themselves. Therefore, three types of interactions are considered : (i) aromatic-aromatic interaction, (ii) aliphatic-aromatic interaction and (iii) aliphatic-aliphatic interaction.

Let A_ϕ be the surface area of aromatic surface (C_6H_5) per mole and A_{CH_3} and A_{CH_2} the surface areas of CH_3 group and CH_2 group per mole respectively. In a binary mixture of two components (1 and 2) the surface areas of components 1 and 2 will be given by

$$A_1 = A_\phi + (n_1 - 1) A_{CH_2} + A_{CH_3} \quad (1)$$

$$A_2 = A_\phi + (n_2 - 1) A_{CH_2} + A_{CH_3} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Fraction of aromatic surface } (\alpha_{1b}) \text{ in pure components 1} = A_\phi / A_1 \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Fraction of aromatic surface } (\alpha_{2b}) \text{ in pure component 2} = A_\phi / A_2 \quad (4)$$

The total surface area of all the molecules in the mixture will be given by

$$A = x_1 A_1 + x_2 A_2 \quad (5)$$

where, n_1 and n_2 represent the number of carbon

atoms in the alkyl chain of molecules of components (1) and (2) respectively, and x_1 and x_2 are their mole fractions.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Total aromatic surface area in the mixture} \\ = (x_1 A_\phi + x_2 A_\phi) = A_\phi \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Fraction of aromatic surface in the mixture} \\ = \frac{A_\phi}{(x_1 A_1 + x_2 A_2)} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Total aliphatic surface area in the mixture} \\ = x_1[(n_1 - 1) A_{CH_2} + A_{CH_3}] + x_2[(n_2 - 1) A_{CH_2} + A_{CH_3}] \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

For simplicity, let us denote the total aliphatic surface area in the mixture by A ,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Fraction of aliphatic} \\ \text{surface area in the mixture} = \frac{A\alpha}{(x_1 A_1 + x_2 A_2)} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

If parameters p , q and r represent respectively, the strength of interactions between aromatic-aromatic surface, aromatic-aliphatic surface and aliphatic-aliphatic surface and assuming random mixing, the configurational enthalpy (H_{conf}) of the binary mixtures can be written as

$$H_{\text{conf}} = A \left[p \left(\frac{A_\phi}{A} \right)^2 + 2q \left(\frac{A_\phi A\alpha}{(A)^2} \right) + r \left(\frac{A\alpha}{A} \right)^2 \right] \quad (10)$$

Then configurational enthalpies H_{conf}^1 and H_{conf}^2 of the pure components 1 and 2 can be obtained from equation (10) by putting $x_1 = 1$ and 0 respectively.

Thus

$$H_{\text{conf}}^1 = A_1 \left[p \left(\frac{A_\phi}{A_1} \right)^2 + 2q \left(\frac{A_\phi A_{\alpha 1}}{(A_1)^2} \right) + r \left(\frac{A_{\alpha 1}}{A_1} \right)^2 \right] \quad (11)$$

$$H_{\text{conf}}^2 = A_2 \left[p \left(\frac{A_\phi}{A_2} \right)^2 + 2q \left(\frac{A_\phi A_{\alpha 2}}{(A_2)^2} \right) + r \left(\frac{A_{\alpha 2}}{A_2} \right)^2 \right] \quad (12)$$

where $A\alpha_1$ and $A\alpha_2$ represent total aliphatic surface areas in components 1 and 2 respectively, and these can be calculated using equations (1) and (2).

Excess enthalpy (H^E) of a binary mixture formed from components 1 and 2 is given by the relation,

$$H^E = H_{\text{conf}} - [x_1 H_{\text{conf}}^1 + x_2 H_{\text{conf}}^2] \quad (13)$$

Using equations (10)–(13), the excess enthalpy of a binary alkylbenzene mixture may be written as

$$H^E = A \left[p \left(\frac{A_\phi}{A} \right)^2 + 2q \left(\frac{A_\phi A_\alpha}{(A)^2} \right) + r \left(\frac{A_\alpha}{A} \right)^2 \right] - x_1 \left[A_1 p \left(\frac{A_\phi}{A_1} \right)^2 + 2q \left(\frac{A_\phi A_{\alpha 1}}{(A_1)^2} \right) + r \left(\frac{A_{\alpha 1}}{A_1} \right)^2 \right] - x_2 \left[A_2 p \left(\frac{A_\phi}{A_2} \right)^2 + 2q \left(\frac{A_\phi A_{\alpha 2}}{(A_2)^2} \right) + r \left(\frac{A_{\alpha 2}}{A_2} \right)^2 \right] \quad (14)$$

After rearrangement, equation (14) simplifies to the form,

$$H^E = \frac{\alpha_{1b}\alpha_{2b} (A_{CH_3})^2 (n_1 - n_2)^2 x_1 x_2 (-p + 2q - r)}{A} \quad (15)$$

or,

$$H^E = k \frac{\alpha_{1b}\alpha_{2b} (A_{CH_3}) (n_1 - n_2)^2 x_1 x_2}{A} \quad (16)$$

where, $k = (-p + 2q - r)$ (17)

Considering vapour phase to be ideal, the configurational enthalpy (H_{conf}) of liquid can be written as

$$H_{\text{conf}} = -(\Delta H_v - RT) \quad (18)$$

where ΔH_v is the enthalpy of vapourisation.

Using equation (11) or (12) and equation (18) the configurational enthalpy of a pure liquid alkylbenzene can be written as

$$A_1 \left[p \left(\frac{A}{A_1} \right)^2 + 2q \left(\frac{A_\phi A_{\alpha 1}}{(A_1)^2} \right) + r \left(\frac{A_{\alpha 1}}{A_1} \right)^2 \right] = -(\Delta H_v - RT) \quad (19)$$

Using equation (19) we have calculated values of p , q and r as $-5.92974 \times 10^{-6} \text{ J cm}^{-2}$, $-3.52016 \times 10^{-6} \text{ J cm}^{-2}$ and $-4.00274 \times 10^{-6} \text{ J cm}^{-2}$ respectively, by the method of the least-squares using ΔH_v values from literature at 298.15 K^1 . Thus knowing the values of p , q and r , enthalpies of vapourisation have been calculated for a number of alkylbenzenes using equation (19). The calculated and experimental ΔH_v values are compared in Table 1. It can be seen that the calculated ΔH_v values show reasonably good agreement with the experimental results.

TABLE 1 – COMPARISON OF EXPERIMENTAL AND CALCULATED (SEMI-EMPIRICAL MODEL) ENTHALPIES OF VAPOURISATION (ΔH_v) OF VARIOUS ALKYL BENZENES AT 298.15 K

Compd	ΔH_v (kJ mol ⁻¹)	
	Expt ^a	Calcd
C ₆ H ₅ CH ₃	37.99	38.18
C ₆ H ₅ C ₂ H ₅	42.25	41.90
C ₆ H ₅ n-C ₃ H ₇	46.23	46.06
C ₆ H ₅ n-C ₄ H ₉	50.12	50.51
C ₆ H ₅ n-C ₅ H ₁₁	55.06	55.16
C ₆ H ₅ n-C ₆ H ₁₃	60.00	59.96
C ₆ H ₅ n-C ₇ H ₁₅	64.94	64.86
C ₆ H ₅ n-C ₈ H ₁₇	69.96	69.84
C ₆ H ₅ n-C ₉ H ₁₉	74.81	74.89

^aRef 1.

During exploratory work, excess enthalpies for various alkylbenzene mixtures were calculated using values of p , q and r as calculated from equation (19), but the calculated H^E showed poor agreement with experimental results. The poor agreement is due to the limited accuracy in enthalpy of vapourisation data used for estimating the values of p , q and r . Therefore, for calculating H^E , the value of $k = 0.43645 \times 10^{-6} \text{ J cm}^{-2}$ (eqn. 16) was estimated empirically from experimental H^E ($x = 0.5$) of ethylbenzene + hexylbenzene mixture at 298.15 K^2 .

The values of surface areas for C₆H₅ group, CH₃ group and CH₂ group have been taken³ as 5.33×10^9 , 2.12×10^9 and $1.35 \times 10^9 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively.

Excess enthalpies ($x = 0.5$) have been calculated for a number of alkylbenzene mixtures using this model and these have been compared with experimental results in Table 2. It can be seen that calculated H^E values show reasonable agreement with the experimental results for ethylbenzene + propylbenzene, + butylbenzene, + amylbenzene and + hexylbenzene; propylbenzene + butylbenzene, + amylbenzene, and + hexylbenzene; + butylbenzene, + amylbenzene and + hexylbenzene; amylbenzene + hexylbenzene. However, calculated H^E for mixtures containing toluene are considerably higher than the experimental results. This large discrepancy could be due to the fact that in toluene the CH_3 group shields the aromatic surface to a larger extent than the adjacent CH_2 group in higher alkylbenzenes and consequently the aromatic surface of toluene available for contact is lesser. Therefore, we adjusted the aromatic surface fraction of toluene using literature H^E ($x = 0.5$) at 298.15 K for toluene + amylbenzene mixture⁶ and recalculated H^E for mixtures containing toluene. The values are given in Table 2. It can be seen that there is improvement in agreement between the experimental and calculated H^E for toluene mixtures.

It may be noted that calculated H^E values using relation (16) for mixtures containing benzene as one of the components are much smaller than the experimental values. Depolarised Rayleigh scattering studies by Clement⁷ indicate the existence of order correlations between benzene molecules in agreement with X-ray diffraction studies⁸ indicating that on average benzene molecules align themselves perpendicularly to each other. However, toluene or ethylbenzene shows no such order correlations. In thermodynamic sense, existence of order corresponds to cohesion which apparently lowers H , S and V of a liquid. Mixing involves net destruction of this order and this loss of order during mixing gives positive contributions to H^E , V^E and S^E . This is reflected in large experimental H^E values for benzene mixtures as compared to alkylbenzene + alkylbenzene mixtures (Table 2). Therefore, we have modified equation (16) for calculating H^E for benzene mixtures which takes into account the order con-

 TABLE 2 - COMPARISON OF EXPERIMENTAL AND CALCULATED (SEMI-EMPIRICAL MODEL) H^E ($x = 0.5$) at 298.15 K

System	H^E (J mol ⁻¹)	
	Expt.	Calcd.*
C ₆ H ₆ + C ₆ H ₅ CH ₃	68.0 ^e	42.2
C ₆ H ₆ + C ₆ H ₅ C ₂ H ₅	98.0 ^f	88.2
C ₆ H ₆ + C ₆ H ₅ n-C ₃ H ₇	142.0 ^d	141.4
C ₆ H ₆ + C ₆ H ₅ n-C ₄ H ₉	186.0 ^d	195.2
C ₆ H ₆ + C ₆ H ₅ n-C ₅ H ₁₁	244.0 ^c	246.8
C ₆ H ₆ + C ₆ H ₅ n-C ₆ H ₁₃	291.0 ^d	295.2
C ₆ H ₅ CH ₃ + C ₆ H ₅ C ₂ H ₅	-8.6 ^a	10.6(3.7)
C ₆ H ₅ CH ₃ + C ₆ H ₅ n-C ₃ H ₇	4.6 ^d	33.9(12.0)
C ₆ H ₅ CH ₃ + C ₆ H ₅ n-C ₄ H ₉	19.1 ^d	62.6(22.1)
C ₆ H ₅ CH ₃ + C ₆ H ₅ n-C ₅ H ₁₁	32.8 ^c	92.9(32.8)
C ₆ H ₅ CH ₃ + C ₆ H ₅ n-C ₆ H ₁₃	53.0 ^d	123.2(43.4)
C ₆ H ₅ C ₂ H ₅ + C ₆ H ₅ n-C ₃ H ₇	8.0 ^d	6.7
C ₆ H ₅ C ₂ H ₅ + C ₆ H ₅ n-C ₄ H ₉	23.2 ^d	22.0
C ₆ H ₅ C ₂ H ₅ + C ₆ H ₅ n-C ₅ H ₁₁	41.8 ^c	41.5
C ₆ H ₅ C ₂ H ₅ + C ₆ H ₅ n-C ₆ H ₁₃	62.9 ^d	62.9
C ₆ H ₅ n-C ₃ H ₇ + C ₆ H ₅ n-C ₄ H ₉	5.8 ^b	4.5
C ₆ H ₅ n-C ₃ H ₇ + C ₆ H ₅ n-C ₅ H ₁₁	16.5 ^c	15.1
C ₆ H ₅ n-C ₃ H ₇ + C ₆ H ₅ n-C ₆ H ₁₃	34.8 ^c	28.9
C ₆ H ₅ n-C ₄ H ₉ + C ₆ H ₅ n-C ₅ H ₁₁	5.3 ^c	3.1
C ₆ H ₅ n-C ₄ H ₉ + C ₆ H ₅ n-C ₆ H ₁₃	12.0 ^c	10.8
C ₆ H ₅ n-C ₅ H ₁₁ + C ₆ H ₅ n-C ₆ H ₁₃	5.3 ^c	2.3

* Figures in parenthesis are values calculated using adjusted aromatic surface fraction of toluene

^aRef. 4 ^bRef. 5 ^cRef. 6 ^dRef. 2. ^eRef. 9 ^fRef. 10

tribution to H^E , i.e. equation (20),

$$H^E = k \frac{\alpha_{1b} \alpha_{2b} (A_{\text{CH}_2})^2 (n_1 - n_2)^2 x_1 x_2}{A} + \{ 20.0 \phi_1 \phi_2 \} \quad (20)$$

where the term in curly brackets represents the order contribution to H^E and ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 represent volume fractions of the two components. Using equation (20) we have calculated H^E for a number of benzene systems (Table 2). It can be seen that except for benzene + toluene system, the calculated values show good agreement with the experimental results.

The composition dependence of H^E for some of the mixtures is shown in Fig. 1. It can be seen that the experimental and calculated H^E - x curves show almost similar symmetrical trends.

Fig. 1. Comparison of experimental and calculated (semi-empirical model) H^E for ethylbenzene (▲) + propylbenzene (Ref. 2), (Δ) + butylbenzene (Ref. 2), (□) + amylbenzene (Ref. 6) and (■) + hexylbenzene (Ref. 2) at 298.15 K. Curves represent calculated values and points represent experimental results. Here, x is the mole fraction of second component in each case.

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References

1. R. C. WILHOIT and B. J. ZOWLINSKI, "Handbook of Vapour Pressures and Heats of Vapourisation of Hydrocarbons and Related Compounds", Thermodynamic Research Centre, Department of Chemistry, Texas A and M University College Station, Texas, 1971.
2. N. S. DHAR, Ph.D. Thesis, Panjab University, Chandigarh, 1991.
3. A. BONDI, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, **68**, 441.
4. W. WOYCICKI, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 1974, **141**, 6.
5. W. WOYCICKI and K. W. SADOWSKA, *Bull. Acad. Pol., Sci. Ser. Sci. Chim.*, 1977, **25**, 115.
6. W. WOYCICKI, *Bull. Acad. Pol., Sci. Ser. Sci. Chim.*, 1977, **25**, 553.
7. C. CLEMENT, *J. Chim. Phys.*, 1978, **75**, 747.
8. A. H. NARTEN, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1977, **67**, 2102.
9. S. MURAKAMI, V. T. LAM and G. C. BENSON, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 1969, **1**, 397.
10. R. TANAKA and G. C. BENSON, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 1976, **8**, 259.